

The Effect of Patient-Centered Communication on Patient Satisfaction: Exploring the Mediating Roles of Interpersonal-based Medical Service Encounters and Patient Trust.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Introduction

The relationship between patient and physician has globally gained widespread attention, recognizing

ABSTRACT

Interaction between patients and healthcare providers, intimate contact, and information sharing have suggested being as essential determinants in medical care services delivery. The purpose of this study is to examine the effect of patient-centered communication (PCC) on patient trust, and patient satisfaction from an interpersonal-based medical service encounters perspective. A structural equation modeling analysis conducted on a dataset of 355 respondents from an online survey filled by outpatients in Togo showed that PCC has a significant positive indirect effect on patient satisfaction through interpersonal-based medical service encounters ($b=0.295$) and patient trust ($b=0.198$). Therefore, implying a full significant mediation of interpersonal-based medical service encounters and patient trust between PCC and patient satisfaction. Results from this study highlighted the significance of having healthcare providers that are well trained in PCC and highly motivated to build patient-provider rapport to improve their patient's satisfaction and healthcare experience.

Keywords: Interpersonal-based medical service encounters, patient-centered communication, patient-provider rapport, trust in healthcare providers, patient satisfaction

communication as such rapport's heartbeat and the critical part of patient-centered care (Rathert, Mittler, Banerjee, & McDaniel, 2017). Several studies have stressed the importance of patient-physician communication and active patient involvement in medical encounters (Dutta-Bergman, 2005; Jiang, 2019b) and their influence on patient health outcomes (Hong & Oh, 2020; Hou & Shim, 2010). Interactive relationship and communication between care providers and patients are healthcare service primary focus, as it is the case in other service industries (marketing and management) (Hsu, 2018; Riviere et al., 2019; Voorhees et al., 2017). It has also been reported that physicians' communication styles promote positive attitudes of consumers toward the quality of service delivered and affect various positive health and health outcomes (Dutta-Bergman, 2005). Patient-centered communication (PCC), also known as "open communication style," which implies patients' active involvement in the relationship, leads to better health-related outcomes and satisfaction (Jiang, 2019a). Aside from the benefits of health outcomes, PCC incorporates patients' satisfaction with their medical care service while strengthening the patient-provider relationship (Hong & Oh, 2020; Trummer, Mueller, Nowak, Stidl, & Pelikan, 2006). Intimate contact, information generation, exchange, and interpretation between health care providers and patients are, therefore, the cornerstone of medical care services provision (Nwosu & Cox, 2000). Patient accords importance to the medical service encounter system such as personal service, physical facilities, and others; as it is part of, and fundamental to, the process of medical services quality evaluation (Chang, Chen, & Lan, 2013; Kim et al., 2017). One of the focal points of patient satisfaction and quality assessment of medical services is their face-to-face interaction with healthcare providers and their decision-making involvement. Studies have shown that direct interactions between patients and service providers produce a positive perceived quality of service and patient satisfaction toward the service delivered (Chang et al., 2013; Chang, Weng, Chang, & Hsu, 2006; Hsu, 2018). Chang et al. (2013) acknowledged the positive influence of patient perception of interpersonal-based medical service encounters on their medical care satisfaction. Additionally, patient trust is considered a vital part of the patient-provider interaction (P. Ward, 2018). Trust is essential for patient involvement in medical decision-making (Petrocchi et al., 2019). Trust also prompts better patient-provider relationship management and improves patient satisfaction (Garrubba & Yap, 2019).

Although there is an increased number of empirical research investigating PCC, the role of providers' behavioral performance during service interactions is of particular interest. According to Epstein and Street's model (2007), PCC's major outcomes are divided into "proximal communication outcome" (e.g., patient-provider interaction and trust) and "intermediate outcomes" (e.g., quality of care, satisfaction). Mapping out PCC's direct and indirect effects on patients' ultimate health would benefit both providers and patients. However, studies that integrate PCC's direct and indirect effects on various positive health outcomes are uncommon. Therefore, this research has attempted to contribute to knowledge using Epstein & Street's (2007) model by assessing and testing the mediating pathways linking PCC to patient satisfaction through interpersonal-based medical service encounters and patient trust in healthcare providers. This paper explored whether PCC helps build a strong patients-providers rapport by affecting providers' behaviors, whether it

enhances patients' trust in health providers, and consequently increases patient satisfaction with the healthcare service received. The following sections describe and discuss the four major variables in this study: PCC and PCC outcomes (i.e., interpersonal-based medical service encounters, trust in healthcare providers, and patients' satisfaction).

Materials and methods

Hypotheses development and conceptual framework

Patient-centered communication

PCC is a central component of patient-centered care to increase care quality. Although PCC concepts vary across studies (Epstein et al., 2005; Mead & Bower, 2000; Robinson, Callister, Berry, & Dearing, 2008), core components are shared. According to Brown (1999), PCC is "a group of communication strategies and behaviors that promote mutuality, shared understandings, and shared decision making in health care encounters." Wanzer et al. (2004) described PCC as "the array of communicative behaviors that can enhance the quality of the relationship between the health care provider and patient, or the patient's family." Moreover, Wanzer et al. (2004) recommend PCC actions to include verbal (introduction by healthcare providers, empathy with patients, careful listening, clarity in explanation, and use of humor) and non-verbal immediacy behaviors (e.g., use of facial gestures, physical distance). Service providers' use of nonverbal and verbal communication is confirmed to be a prerequisite for a successful service encounter (Fassaert, van Dulmen, Schellevis, & Bensing, 2007; Lin & Lin, 2017).

Epstein et al. (2005) identified PCC as a means to improve patient-centeredness during contact between patients and care providers. Patient-centeredness is considered a three-core moral philosophy: "(1) considering patients' needs, wants, perspectives and individual experiences"; "(2) offering patients opportunities to provide input into and participate in their care"; and "(3) enhancing partnership and understanding in the patient-physician relationship." They defined PCC as care that addresses patients' perspectives, considers patients within their psychosocial context; achieves a common understanding of patients' issues and treatments; and involves patients in the care and decisions related to their health (Epstein & Street Jr, 2007). The latter is an essential aspect of PCC because, through shared decision-making, patients' informational and emotional needs are met. However, sharing decision-making does not imply sharing all information nor assigning all responsibilities to the patient, but only "taking into account the patient's desire for information and for sharing decision making and responding appropriately" (Stewart, 2001).

In this research, PCC is regarded as the main variable that strengthens relationships between patients and providers and affects the overall health quality assessments. Patients' perception of PCC is the strongest predictor of healthcare efficiency and health outcomes (Stewart, 2001). Thus, PCC here indicates patients' perception of PCC, not the experts' perception. In most cases, patients can perceive PCC correctly than assessing the overall medical quality-hence the emphasis here. PCC's practice by health professionals must be appropriate and reliable enough to be understood and accepted by patients.

Patient-centered communication, interpersonal-based medical service encounters, and patient trust.

Interpersonal-based medical service encounters involve direct interactions between providers and consumers during service delivery and consumption (M. R. Solomon, Surprenant, Czepiel, & Gutman, 1985). Service encounters are perceived to be a central aspect in most service-marketing activities. It significantly influences service quality management, delivery mechanisms, and customer satisfaction (Chang et al., 2006).

Interpersonal communication is essential in forming connections (Dimbleby & Burton, 1992), creating, maintaining, and modifying relationships (D. H. Solomon & Vangelisti, 2014). Thus, a good and robust customer-employee rapport is developed with appropriate communication. Some authors believe that PCC establishes a stronger patient-provider rapport by enhancing "mutual trust, respect, and commitment" (Epstein & Street Jr, 2007; Ranjan, Kumari, & Chakrawarty, 2015), which leads to outcomes that go beyond interaction. Lin et al. (2017) concluded that non-verbal communication significantly improves the rapport between the customer and the employee. Gremler et al. (2008) also found that employee verbal communication practices, such as common grounding and information exchange, help cultivate and build rapport.

Additionally, customers frequently seek clues during service encounters to judge service performances (Anderson & Smith, 2016); PCC, therefore, might be one factor that can increase patients' perception of their rapport with providers for a better judgment of and commitment toward the service. The above discussion offers firm evidence supporting the first hypothesis by suggesting a link between PCC and interpersonal-based medical service encounters, as follows:

H1: Patients' perception of PCC will significantly affect their perception of interpersonal-based medical service encounters.

Trust is an integral part of any patient-provider relationship. Fiscella, in 2004, showed that the more physicians practice PCC, the higher patients report trust. In their study, Hong et al. (2020) also reported the significant influence of PCC on patient trust in medical care providers and healthcare quality assessment. Thus, we propose the relation between PCC and patient trust in the next hypothesis:

H2: Patients' perception of PCC positively influences their trust in healthcare providers.

Patient-centered communication and patient satisfaction

According to Pizam et al. (2016), "Customer satisfaction is a psychological concept that involves the feeling of well-being and pleasure that results from obtaining what one hopes for and expects from an appealing product and service." Concerning the service delivery outcomes or process, satisfaction has been defined as "the end state resulting from the experience of consumption." (Pizam, Shapoval, & Ellis, 2016). Consequently, customer satisfaction mirrors a delivered product or service's perceived performance based on a comparison of outcomes with expectations (J.-H. Kim, 2018).

Previous studies and reviews have reported a positive association between health providers' communication

skills or patient perception of PCC and patient satisfaction (Altin & Stock, 2016; Jiang, 2017; King & Hoppe, 2013; Larson, Leslie, & Kruk, 2017; Ranjan et al., 2015; Wanzer, Booth-Butterfield, & Gruber, 2004), patient's recall, understanding and adherence (Bartlett et al., 1984; Hahn, 2009; Molfenter & Brown, 2014; Richard, Glaser, & Lussier, 2017). For example, in a narrative review summarizing studies on patient-provider communication, King et al. (2013) found that health providers' communication behaviors led to positive patient outcomes. Altin et al. (2016), assessing predictors of satisfaction with the care received among German adults, reported that respondents that have received an easy and understandable explanation of things and engaged in decision making about their treatment are 4.44 times and 4.02 times more likely to report satisfaction than others, respectively.

Wanzer et al. (2004) differentiated satisfaction into satisfaction toward communication and satisfaction toward medical care. By applying the theory of uncertainty and reduction, they claimed that interaction among doctors and patients with PCC approaches minimizes patient anxiety and uncertainty and enhance the degree of both types of patient satisfaction. Similarly, October et al. (2016) assess the relationship between physicians' PCC behaviors and parent satisfaction during the PICU parent-physician conferences. They argued that interactions between parent and physician involving more patient-centered components, including higher levels of empathic explanations, emotional conversations, and questioning, significantly affect parent satisfaction regardless of the intensity of the child's disease. Based on the above literature, the next hypothesis was:

H3: Patient perception of PCC positively influences satisfaction with the medical service.

The mediating role of interpersonal-based medical service encounters and patient trust

According to Chang et al. (2006), the pro-social behavior of frontline medical workers such as doctors and nurses, the way services are provided, as well as the individual interactions are critical to patients' satisfaction and evaluation of medical services (Chang et al., 2013; Mechinda & Patterson, 2011). Numerous researches have been performed examining service encounters from the point of view of customer and service staff (Chang et al., 2006; Hausman, 2004; Kim et al., 2017; Winsted, 2000; Zhao, Yan, & Keh, 2018). They argued that service personnel behaviors strongly affect patient compliance, participation, satisfaction, and medical service quality evaluation. For example, Chang et al. (2013) argued that the perception of interpersonal-based medical service encounters positively affects patient satisfaction.

Moreover, the physical surroundings where services are delivered, particularly in service industries (such as hotels, restaurants, and hospitals), strongly influence behaviors and image creations (Bitner, 1992). Numerous studies have shown that the physical environment significantly affects customers' emotional reactions, satisfaction, and behavior in service settings (Bitner, Booms, & Tetreault, 1990; Lee, Chua, & Han, 2017). Since the service industry's service production and consumption happen concurrently, customers "in the factory" experience the services inside the firms' physical facilities. Hence, the physical environment can significantly influence the customers' perceptions and evaluations of the service experience.

Trust is indispensable to establish a stable and healthy relationship between patient and provider (Bova et al., 2012). It is unanimous that patients increased level of trust in doctors is related to better patient practices and health outcomes. A considerable amount of studies suggests that patient trust in doctors affects patients' willingness to seek and use healthcare services, uptake of preventive services (Ward, 2017). Besides, patient trust has proven to affect satisfaction and other health-related behaviors. For instance, Chang et al. (2013) have shown that patient trust has a positive effect on satisfaction. The above discussion presents a clear case for the following hypotheses, which suggested that PCC, trust in healthcare providers, and satisfactions are connected as follows:

H4: Perceived interpersonal-based medical service encounters mediates the influence of PCC on patient satisfaction

H5: Trust in healthcare providers mediates PCC's influence on patient satisfaction.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework

Methods

Participants and procedure

This survey study relied on primary data collected from outpatients in Togo's four most visited public hospitals. The study focused on outpatients aged 18 or older, receiving medical service, or who have visited these hospitals in the past 12 months. A professional translator translated all items in the questionnaire, initially created in English, into French. Another professional translator and one graduate student translated the French version back into English to guarantee its correctness and accuracy. The French version was approved after analyzing items. A sum of 363 questionnaires was gathered from the study respondents. 355 questionnaires were statistically analyzed after discarding eight invalid questionnaires (e.g., due to contradictory responses).

Measurements

The questionnaire in this study was meticulously built based on previous literature. It comprised cinq sections: demographics, patient satisfaction, patient trust in healthcare service providers, PCC, and interpersonal-based medical service encounters.

We assessed Patient satisfaction using four items obtained from the Short Assessment of Patient Satisfaction North American Academic Research, 4(1) | 2021 | <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4479730> Monthly Journal by TWASP, USA | 214

(Hawthorne, Sansoni, Hayes, Marosszeky, & Sansoni, 2014; Jiang, 2019). Respondents scored patient satisfaction regarding healthcare service received over a 12 months duration using a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1=very dissatisfied to 5= very satisfied. The sample items included "How satisfied are you with the effect of your (treatment/care)?" and "How satisfied are you with the explanations the (doctor/other health professionals) provided?"

Trust in healthcare providers and interpersonal-based medical service encounter measures were adopted (Chang et al., 2013) and (Hong & Oh, 2020). Five items with a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree applied to measure trust in health providers. Respondents were required to score their agreement on the five items. The sample items included "I can trust medical care personnel's judgment on my sickness," and "Medical care personnel will honor the agreement made with the patients." Using a 5-point Likert scale on 13 items ranging from 1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree, we measured Interpersonal-based medical service encounters. Respondents have been required to rate their agreement with these 13 items, such as "I feel the nurses are professional during the whole treatment process" and "Service counter personnel are able to provide answers that solve my doubts."

PCC was measured by six items adapted from (Hong & Oh, 2020; Wanzer et al., 2004). Respondents were urged to indicate to what degree doctors and other healthcare providers used specific types of PCC. A 5-point Likert scale was implored, ranging from 1=never to 5=very often was employed to assess patient perception of PCC behavior. The items include "They listened carefully to me when talking with them," and "They involved me in decisions about my health care."

Data Analysis

Statistical software packages SPSS 25.0 and AMOS 14.0 were used for data analyses and processing. The analysis consists of determining the sample characteristics using the descriptive statistical analysis and performing structural equation modeling (SEM) analysis. SEM was performed to illustrate the nature of the relationship between the variables and the direction of cause-effect accordingly. Thus, hypotheses 1 to 5 were checked using SEM. Indices such as Chi-square ratio (<3), the goodness of fit index ($GFI >.9$), adjusted goodness of fit index ($AGFI >.8$), normal fit index ($NFI >.9$), and root mean square of standardized residual ($RMSR <.08$), were used to measure the overall fitness.

Results

Descriptive statistics

The analysis was conducted based on 355 respondents who visited one or more times a healthcare provider (doctors, nurses, or another health provider) during the last 12 months. For the number of visits a year, the majority (35.5%) visited five times and more, followed by a one-time visit (24.2%), two times visit (20.6%), three times (13.5%), and four times (6.2%).

Overall, the respondents include male (67%) and female (33%) respondents, among which the majority are single (74.9%). Demographic statistics showed that 67.3% of participants were aged 18-30 years, 30.4% were 31-45 years, and only 1.7% and 0.6% were between 46-60 years and more than 60. Furthermore, most participants had master and undergraduate education (42.8% and 38%, respectively), 15.8% had postgraduate education, and 10.4% completed high school. Table 1 provides the descriptive statistics of the main variables and their correlations.

Table 1: Correlation, Means, and standard deviations.

	M	SD	PCC	IBMSE	PT	PS
PCC	3.33	.73	1			
IBMSE	2.66	.62	.695**	1		
PT	3.21	.71	.699**	.707**	1	
PS	3.53	.80	.697**	.815**	.835**	1

Note. N = 355, PCC indicates Patient-centered communication, PT indicates patient trust, PS is patient satisfaction, and IBMSE indicates Interpersonal-based medical service encounters;

**p < .01

Hypotheses testing

In order to test the measurement model, a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was performed using AMOS 24. The four-factor model with interpersonal-based medical service encounters as a second-order factor of Professional personal, General administrative personal, and environment and space (physical surroundings) was tested. The first-order factor, "Professional personnel" of interpersonal-based medical service encounters, one item each of the first-order factors General administrative personnel and environment and space, one item of PCC, two items of patient trust were dropped to meet model fit, and validity and reliability criteria. The fitting of the measurement model was acceptable (see Table2). The model also fulfilled validity and reliability requirements such as composite reliability (CR > .70), average variance extracted (AVE > .50), and the AVE square root higher than the inter construct correlations (Fornell & Larcker, 1981), see table3. We did a method bias test with a common latent factor and found that the unconstrained model was significantly different from the constrained to zero models. Therefore, we have a bias, and we accounted for the bias when creating our factor scores for SEM analysis.

Table2: Model fit measures using Amos plugin (Gaskin & Lim, 2016)

Measure	Estimate	Threshold	Interpretation
CMIN	363.000	--	--
DF	127.000	--	--
CMIN/DF	2.858	Between 1 and 3	Excellent
CFI	0.930	>0.95	Acceptable
SRMR	0.054	<0.08	Excellent
RMSEA	0.072	<0.06	Acceptable

Table3: Model validity measures using Amos plugin (Gaskin, J.2019)

	CR	AVE	PCC	PS	PT	IBMSE
PCC	0.841	0.516	0.719			
PS	0.886	0.660	0.636***	0.812		
PT	0.799	0.573	0.663***	0.755***	0.757	
IBMSE	0.830	0.716	0.658***	0.687***	0.636***	0.846

Note: PCC indicates Patient-centered communication, PT indicates patient trust, PS is patient satisfaction, and IBMSE indicates Interpersonal-based medical service encounters.

A path analysis was performed to test the hypotheses. Gender, age, education, and the number of visits have been included as control variables to predict all endogenous variables. The test of the path model showed a satisfactory fit: $\chi^2 (6) = 26.458$, $p < .001$, CFI=.982, RMSEA=.098, SRMR = .0455. The results of the path analysis are illustrated in figure 2.

Figure2: Results of the structural model

Note. Control variables are not included in the figure for a parsimonious presentation. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

Hypotheses H1 and H2, respectively, predicted a positive influence of PCC on interpersonal-based medical service encounters and patient trust. As anticipated, PCC was positively related with interpersonal-based medical service encounters (standardized $b = .70$, $p < .001$), and with patient trust (standardized $b = .40$, $p < .001$). Therefore, both H1 and H2 were supported.

We predicted that the PCC would positively influence patient satisfaction (H3); however, the result showed no significant relation between PCC and patient satisfaction (unstandardized $b = .054$, $p = .177$).

The path between interpersonal-based medical service encounters and patient satisfaction ($b = .42$, $p < .001$) and between patient trust and patient satisfaction ($b = .50$, $p < .001$) were statistically significant. The last group of hypotheses relates to PCC's indirect effect on patient satisfaction through interpersonal-based medical service encounters (H4) and patient trust (H5). PCC's total indirect effect on patient satisfaction was significant statistically (standardized indirect effect = .647, $p = 0.001$, bootstrapped 95% CI = .578 to .725). Assessing the specific indirect effect, we found a positive indirect effect of PCC on patient satisfaction via interpersonal-based medical service encounters (standardized indirect effect = .295, $p < 0.001$, bootstrapped 95% CI = .258 to .389) and via patient trust (standardized indirect effect = .198, $p < 0.001$, bootstrapped 95% CI = .163 to .277). In brief, H4 and H5 were supported, indicating that the mediation effect of interpersonal-based medical service encounters and patient trust in the PCC-satisfaction relationship was significant.

Additionally, we found that the path between interpersonal-based medical service encounters and patient trust was statistically significant ($b=.44, p < .001$). Therefore, confirming PCC's positive indirect effect on patient satisfaction through interpersonal-based medical service encounters and patient trust (standardized indirect effect=.307, $p < 0.001$, bootstrapped 95% CI=.126 to .218).

Results of all direct and indirect effects are reported in table 4.

Table 4. Direct and Indirect effect on patient satisfaction. *** $p < 0.001$

Indirect Path	Lower	Upper	P-Value	Standardized Estimate
PCC --> IBMSE --> PT --> PS	0.126	0.218	0.001	0.307***
PCC --> IBMSE --> PS	0.258	0.389	0.001	0.295***
PCC --> PT --> PS	0.163	0.277	0.001	0.198***
Direct Path	Lower	Upper	P-Value	Standardized Estimate
PCC-->IBMSE	0.628	0.761	0.001	0.702***
PCC-->PT	0.297	0.501	0.001	0.397***
PCC-->PS	-0.023	0.130	0.180	0.05
IBMSE-->PS	0.338	0.502	0.001	0.42***
PT-->PS	0.414	0.596	0.001	0.50***

Note: PCC indicates Patient-centered communication, PT indicates patient trust, PS is patient satisfaction, and IBMSE indicates Interpersonal-based medical service encounters.

Discussion

This research aimed to investigate the relationship between perception of PCC, interpersonal-based medical service encounters, patient trust, and satisfaction with the medical care service. We also tested the mediating role of interpersonal-based medical service encounters and patient trust in PCC's effect on patient satisfaction. To summarize the significant findings, we first found that the patient's perception of PCC positively influences patients' perception of interpersonal-based medical service encounters and trust. This finding supports

previous studies' assertions highlighting PCC's effect on patient-provider rapport and patient trust in healthcare service providers (Hong & Oh, 2020; Lin & Lin, 2017).

Contrary to previous studies (Wanzer et al., 2004); PCC perception did not significantly influence patient satisfaction. Instead, PCC's perception positively influences patient satisfaction through interpersonal-based medical service encounters and patient trust; interpersonal-based medical service encounters and trust in healthcare providers fully mediated PCC's effect on patient satisfaction. Such findings are in accordance with Epstein and Street's (2007) model, which recommended pathways connecting providers and patients to health outcomes by an intimate communication outcome and an intermediate outcome. In this study, we applied (a) interpersonal-based medical service encounters and patients' trust in healthcare providers as close outcomes of communication, and (b) patient satisfaction as an intermediate outcome of a range of possible outcome variables suggested by Epstein and Street (2007). Therefore, this study also contributed to the model testing of Epstein and Street (Street et al., 2009) by providing empirical support.

Furthermore, PCC's indirect effect on satisfaction via Interpersonal-based medical service encounters is greater than the impact via patient trust. This finding implies that physicians' and nurses' performance and behavior, the effort made by spending time interacting with patients to establish a more powerful bond, and the comfortable environment for the treatment are important aspects for patient satisfaction.

Additionally, perceived Interpersonal-based medical service encounters positively influence patient trust in healthcare providers, leading to their satisfaction. Thus, PCC affected patient satisfaction via both interpersonal-based medical service encounters and patient trust. These results show the importance of medical care and general service personnel's attitudes, demonstrating interpersonal-based behaviors by developing a trust relationship that enhances patient satisfaction. The exhibition of caring behaviors from healthcare providers, such as professional personnel, general administrative personnel, as well as the environment and space is highly essential factors in building patient trust leading to patient satisfaction (Chang et al., 2013; Dang, Westbrook, Njue, & Giordano, 2017; Murray & McCrone, 2015).

Several practical implications can be obtained from the findings of this study for hospitals and medical institutions. They should consider PCC when attempting to establish patients' needs, thereby improving their healthcare service experience and satisfaction. Instead, patients would participate actively during their medical treatment by engaging in a conversation with their caregivers, explaining their desires and preferences, and their concerns and questions. Therefore, healthcare providers should facilitate open communication and provide explicit consent and encouragement, allowing patients to ask questions. The implementation of PCC among employees would be a good starting point for hospitals pursuing better outcomes and enhancing positive verbal reports, patients' loyalty and retention, and possible recommendations to future patients. The results illustrate the importance of provider-patient interactions and highlight professional personnel and the general administrative role. Patients' higher perception of PCC leads to a higher perception of professional personnel skills, interpersonal skills, and personal characteristics that contribute to a relationship of trust between providers and patients. Moreover, a trusting relationship based on the health providers' decent

behavior during the interpersonal-based medical service encounters significantly affects patients' satisfaction (Chang et al., 2013). Based on such findings, we suggest that hospitals improve their staff skills, behavioral habits, and staff personal communication attitudes to retain patients and build trusting relationships.

Mainly, PCC requires commitment and practice from healthcare providers before it becomes habitual behavior. Hence, PCC should be implemented and enforced in the entire healthcare system to ensure quality service delivery longevity. All healthcare personnel should be trained in PCC as excellent training can positively affect providers' behaviors toward patients in the interpersonal-based medical encounter (Wanzer et al., 2004). Healthcare providers should be trained routinely and adequately to practice PCC behaviors with various patients in challenging situations flexibly. Besides, PCC includes focusing and listening more to patients; hence, providers' average consultation time will be increased, thus needs to be compensated (Hong & Oh, 2020). Hospitals, medical institutions, health systems, and policy-makers' bodies should, therefore, consider these barriers while supporting PCC behaviors among healthcare providers.

PCC mostly discussed from the patients' viewpoints, is beneficial not only for patients but also for providers, as they would enjoy the benefit of trust developed with patients. They can also anticipate patients following their recommended prescription and treatments, leading to tremendous improvement in patients' cures and optimal health outcomes achievement. For example, patients become subjects to non-expert online sources when they lack trust in the health care provider (Hou & Shim, 2010). Moreover, patients have recently become acquainted with their health by accessing broad health information and prefer to engage in healthcare decisions (Finney Rutten et al., 2015). PCC can be that tool through which health information acquired from other various sources is discussed to improve health outcomes and patient-provider relationships (Liu & Jiang, 2019; Tan & Goonawardene, 2017). Through PCC adoption, healthcare professionals may encourage patients to share the knowledge obtained from online sources, correct them if irrelevant, and guide them to more relevant information sources. PCC can thus contribute to improved outcomes for patients as well as health care providers.

Limitations and suggestions for future research

This study identified the following limitation. First, the survey sample of online respondents over 45 years old restricts the findings' generalizability. Future works should preferably utilize the probability-sampling technique, which includes participants of a different group of age. Secondly, this study investigated the mediation role of interpersonal-based medical service encounters and trust while controlling four other factors. Epstein and Street (2007) suggested various mediators and moderators affecting patient-provider communication and outcomes. Moderators include cultural and social (e.g., social support, cultural beliefs), demographics (e.g., gender, age, race), and education factors. Future research should assess the relevance of the mediating relations identified in this research in other countries, examine the moderators mentioned above, and include more controlled unmeasured confounding variables (four in this study).

Furthermore, although several previous studies examining interpersonal-based medical service encounters have used similar scales (e.g., Chang et al., 2013), we dropped the item "professional personnel" to meet validity criteria when measuring interpersonal-based medical service encounters. Thus, it would be meaningful and significant for a future study to include all aspects when observing patients' perceptions of healthcare providers' interpersonal-based medical service encounters. Our findings also agree that various aspect of PCC, such as physician's empathy skills, immediacy, and listening ability; nurse's empathy skills; and healthcare providers staff (physician, nurse, and other staff) introduction and clarity affect patients' satisfaction with communication (Wanzer et al., 2004). Hence, it is pertinent for future studies to analyze patients' expectations for PCC in all its aspects and their links to the sub-dimensions of interpersonal-based medical service encounters. It is also conceivable that the relationship represents a reversed causal effect between PCC and interpersonal-based medical service encounters, meaning that, as patients perceive interpersonal-based medical service encounters, their interaction with healthcare providers is more likely regarded as highly patient-centered. Future studies should proceed with this research line to assess the reverse causal effect between PCC and interpersonal-based medical service encounters.

Conclusion

In this study, we focus on how PCC enhances patient satisfaction focusing on the mediating role of interpersonal-based medical service encounters and patient trust. Our study's findings suggest that PCC has a significant indirect effect on patient satisfaction through mediators, interpersonal-based medical service encounters, and patient trust. Nowadays, patients are continuously aware due to the increasing means of searching for information. Therefore, the healthcare organizations should prioritize interaction with patients. Considering the growing patient awareness, medical care organizations should encourage health providers by adopting PCC behaviors as well as interpersonal-based medical service encounters to foster patient trust and enhance patient satisfaction. Medical managers should emphasize customer-oriented rather than sales-oriented services to encourage PCC create the patient's value, and work towards improving patients' satisfaction and increasing their well-being and quality of life.

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